

“A Study of Capital Budgeting of Fountainhead Info solutions Pvt.Ltd.”

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ABSTRACT:

Such decisions can be investment decisions, financing decisions or operating decisions. Investment decisions deal with investment of organization's resources in Long term (fixed) Assets and / or Short term (Current) Assets. Decisions pertaining to investment in Short term Assets fall under “Working Capital Management”. Decisions pertaining to investment in Long term Assets are classified as “Capital Budgeting” decisions.

Keywords: Investment decisions, financing decisions, Capital Budgeting

1. INTRODUCTION:

A proficient portion of capital is the most significant account work in present day times. It includes choices to submit company's assets to long haul resources. Such choices are will in general decide the estimation of organization/firm by affecting its development, gainfulness and hazard.

Entire choices are commonly known as capital planning or capital use choices. It is sharp choices to put current in long haul resources expecting long haul benefits company's speculation choices would by and large incorporate extension, securing, modernization and substitution of long haul resources. Such choices can be speculation choices, financing choices or working choices.

Speculation choices manage venture of association's assets in Long term (fixed) Assets and/or Short term (Current) Assets. Choices relating to interest in Short term Assets fall under "Working Capital Management". Choices relating to interest in Long term Assets are named "Capital Budgeting".

2. NEED FOR THE STUDY:

The Research Paper is embraced to break down and comprehend the Capital Budgeting process in back office administration segment. This gives me a hazardous to handy ramifications of hypothetical information. To think about the organization's activity of utilizing different Capital Budgeting strategies. To know how the organization gets assets from different sources.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To consider the significance of capital planning in assessing the undertaking for venture account.
2. To consider the strategy of capital planning for dynamic.
3. To quantify the current estimation of rupee contributed.
4. To understand an item wise study of the financial performance of the company.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

“Research is a structured enquiry that utilizes acceptable scientific methodology to solve problems and create new knowledge that is generally applicable”.

“Research is a careful or critical inquiry or examination in seeking facts or principles; diligent investigation in order to ascertaining something”.

DATA SOURCES

These secondary data is existing data which is already been collected by others, for that the sources are financial journals, annual reports of the FOUNTAINHEAD INFO SOLUTIONS PVT. LTD. website and other Publications.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

Non availability of time is another confining variable, i.e., the schedule time of about a month and a half are not satisfactory to make the assessment independently as for Capital Budgeting in Fountainhead. The clamoring schedule of the experts in the Fountainhead is another obliging variable. On account of the clamoring timetable specialists limited me to assemble the complete information about affiliation. Non-availability of characterized budgetary data. The examination is coordinated in a short period, which was not point by point in all edges.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Profitability Index All these methods of capital budgeting techniques are explained in detail – below:

1. PAY BACK PERIOD:

The Pay Back Period is one the most popular and most widely recognized traditional method of evaluating investment proposals. It is defined as the number of years required in a project. If the project generates constant annual cash inflows, the payback period can be computed by the following formulae:

Initial Investment

$$\text{Pay Back Period} = \frac{\text{Initial Investment}}{\text{Annual Cash Flow}}$$

In case of unequal cash inflows, the payback period can be computed by calculating the cumulative cash inflow and checking whether the values are recovered to the original outlay and taking the remaining amount and apply the formulae i.e.,

$$\text{PBP} = \text{base year} + \frac{\text{Required CFAT}}{\text{Next year CFAT}}$$

STATEMENT SHOWING CALCULATION OF PAY BACK PERIOD (Rs. in Lakh)

YEAR	ROE (Return on equity)	Income	TAX	Profit After Tax	DEP	Cash Flow After Tax	CCFAT
1	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	235.52
2	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	471.04
3	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	706.56
4.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	942.08
5.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	1177.60
6.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	1413.12
7.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	1648.64
8.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	1884.16
9	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	2119.68
10.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12	170.40	235.52	2355.20
11.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2411.72
12.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2468.24
13.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2524.76
14.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2581.28
15.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2637.80
16.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2694.32
17.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2750.84
18.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2807.36
19.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2863.88
20.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2920.40
21.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	2976.92
22.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	3033.44
23.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	3089.96
24.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	3146.48
25.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32	14.20	56.52	3203.00

Base Year = 9th Year Required CFAT=10.32 for Next year CFAT =235.52
2130-2119.68

Payback Period =9 year + ----- =9th year + .00437 yr.
2355.20

Interpretation:

As per payback period, the project is accepted because to get the initial investment of 2130 lakhs, it is taking a time of 9.004 years.

2. AVERAGE RATE OF RETURN:

The Average Rate OF Return (ARR) is also known as Accounting Rate of Return using accounting information, as revealed by financial statement, to measure the profitability of an investment. The accounting rate of return is found out by dividing the average after tax profit by the average investment. The average investment would be equal to half of the original investment, if it is depreciated constantly .The Accounting rate of return can be calculated by the following formula i.e.,

$$\text{A.R.R} = \frac{\text{Annual Average Profit after Tax}}{\text{Annual Average investment}} \times 100$$

STATEMENT SHOWING CALCULATION OF AVERAGE RATE OF RETURN (Rs. in Lakhs)

YEAR	ROE	INC	TAX	PAT
1.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
2.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
3.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
4.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
5.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
6.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
7.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
8.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
9.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12
10.	59.64	5.48	0	65.12

11.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
12.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
13.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
14.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
15.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
16.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
17.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
18.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
19.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
20.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
21.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
22.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
23.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
24.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
25.	59.64	5.48	22.8	42.32
Total				1286.00

CALCULATION OF ARR:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Average NPAT} &= 1286/25 = 51.44 \\ \text{Average Investment} &= 2130/2 = 1065. \\ &51.44 \\ \text{ARR} &= \frac{\text{-----}}{1065} \times 100 = 4.83 \% \end{aligned}$$

Interpretation:

From the point of ARR method, project should be accepted, as its ARR is less than the required rate of return (4.83% < 12%).

3. NET PRESENT VALUE

The Net present Value (NPV) method is the classic economic method of evaluating the investment proposals. It is one of the discounted cash flow techniques explicitly recognizing the time value of money. It correctly postulates that cash flows arising at different time periods differ in value and the comparable only when their equivalent present values are found out.

A project may be accepted in NPV = 0.

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Thus, the NPV acceptance rules are:

Accept if NPV > 0 ▪ Reject if NPV < 0

Ill-defined if NPV= 0.

Initial investment -- Rs: 4, 00,000

Annual Cash Flow -- Rs: 1, 00, 000

Life of the project -- Rs: 10 years

DCF rate of return (say) -- 21.4%

Year	Capital in the beginning of the year	Net Surplus in the year	Payment of interest @21.41%	Recovery of capital	Capital at the end of the year
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
1	4,00,000	1,00,000	85,652	14,348	3,85,652
2	3,85,652	1,00,000	85,580	17,420	3,68,232
3	3,68,232	1,00,000	78,919	21,081	3,47,151
4	3,47,151	1,00,000	74,335	25,665	3,21,486
5	3,21,486	1,00,000	63,840	31,160	2,90,326
6	2,90,326	1,00,000	62,168	37,832	2,52,494
7	2,52,494	1,00,000	54,067	45,933	2,06,561
8	2,06,561	1,00,000	44,231	55,769	1,50,792
9	1,50,792	1,00,000	32,289	67,711	83,081
10	83,081	1,00,000	17,790	82,210	871
				3,99,129	

6.FINDINGS:

1. It is estimated that a capital requirements of 2crores is required to complete the thousands of projects already included in existing projects.
2. Actual realization of rate of return projected in at the time of project appraisal will depend on timely completion of project without any time over run and cost overrun.
3. From the Revenue budget for the year 2018-2019, it is clear that the Actual sales (Rs. 16855250) are more than the budgeted or estimated sales (Rs. 16420854). It is a good sign and the overall earnings of the budget indicate high volume over estimated.
4. New projects acceptance consider on the basis of Return Benefits. Risk is evaluated while considering the new projects.

7.SUGGESTIONS:-

1. Actual realization of rate of return projected in at the time of project appraisal will depend on timely completion of project without any time over run and cost overrun.
2. The Corporate mission of Fountainhead is to make available reliable and quality power in increasingly large quantities.
3. The organization needs the capable personalities as management to lead to organization successfully. The management makes the plans and implement of these plans. These plans are expressed in terms of long-term investment decisions.
4. The special budgets are rarely used in the organization like long-term budgets, research & development budget and budget and budget for constancy.

8. CONCLUSION:

The NPV method followed on Fountainhead is satisfactory. In this method, the unit Cost Worked out by costing department of Fountainhead is adopted. The unit costs are updated continuously i.e., every year after closure of Financial Accounts of Fountainhead. In the project for studying the methods of financial evaluation of Fountainhead projects it is seen the rate of return is estimated 17% to 22%.

Each association has pre-decided arrangement of goal and objectives, yet arriving at those targets and objectives just by legitimate arranging and executing of the plans financially.

9. REFERENCES:

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